

Synthesis of 3-Aryl-6-methyl-7-phenyl-8-oxo-2H,8H-pyrano[3,2-g][1,4]benzoxazines as Potent Antimicrobial Agents

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It is established that angular coumarin-oxazine derivatives¹ exhibit antifungal activity, with a view to evaluating and comparing their biological activity with angular analogues, we have undertaken the synthesis of linear coumarinoxazine derivatives.

The condensation of 6-amino-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-phenylcoumarin² (1) with various ω -bromoacetophenones³ (2) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate-acetone, yielded respective 3-aryl-6-methyl-7-phenyl-8-oxo-2H,8H-pyrano[3,2-g][1,4]benzoxazine-(3a-e) which were characterised by their analytical and spectral data.

The ir bands of 3a-e appeared at 1620-1590 (C=N) and 1330-1160 and 1100-1070 cm⁻¹ of symmetric and asymmetric stretching of the aliphatic and aromatic ether system respectively⁴, which are totally absent in the spectrum of its precursor (1) and confirms the cyclisation to 3a-e. All compounds revealed the absorption bands as expected, along with a band at 1730-1700 cm⁻¹ for the lactone carbonyl group⁵.

The pmr spectrum of 3e contained a neat three-proton singlet at δ 2.3 due to C-6 methyl group. Another three-proton singlet which appeared at δ 4.00 is due to methoxy group of 3-phenyl ring attached to oxazine nucleus. The C-2 methylene group of oxazine nucleus appeared as a singlet at δ 5.05. A complex multiplet appeared around δ 6.8-8.0 integrating for eleven aromatic protons.

The mass spectra of 3a-e exhibited a general fragmentation pattern. In almost all the spectra, it is observed that loss of aryl acetylene or phenyl or CO group converting it into the corresponding fragments is the predominant pattern.

Biological activity: Compounds 3a-e were screened for their antibacterial activity by the filter paper disc diffusion plate method⁶ and for their antifungal activity by the food poisoning technique⁷.

The antibacterial activity was carried out against the microorganisms *Bacillus megaterium* and *Proteus vulgaris*. All the compounds were found less toxic towards the bacteria tested. The relatively high toxicity of compound 3d may be attributed to *p*-nitrophenyl moiety.

The antifungal activity was tested against *Fusarium solani* and *Dreschelera specifera*. All the compounds were found toxic whereas 3a and 3c less toxic. The compounds showed maximum inhibition at 800 μ g ml⁻¹. Compounds 3d and 3e showed 100% inhibition in both the fungi at 800 μ g ml⁻¹. In general, the linear coumarinoxazines exhibited less antibacterial and antifungal activities than those of their angular analogues¹.

Experimental

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D-300 spectrometer at 70 eV.

3-Aryl-6-methyl-7-phenyl-8-oxo-2H,8H-pyrano[3,2-g][1,4]benzoxazines (3a-e). **General procedure:** A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2.07 g, 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (250 ml) was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The ω -bromoacetophenones (0.01 mol) were then added and the mixture was refluxed for 24 h. The excess of acetone was distilled off and the residue washed with ice-cold water (150 ml), filtered and the solid recrystallised from suitable solvents: 3a (60%), m.p. 170°, m/z

NOTES

367 (M^+ , 100), 366 (22.77), 352 (6.25), 339 (62.5), 290 (3.68), 265 (17.18), 236 (60), 103 (90.6) and 77 (62), δ 6.9–8.0 (m, ArH), 5.6 (s, 2-H), 2.3 (s, 6-CH₃); **3b** (58%), m.p. 166°, δ 7.0–8.2 (m, ArH), 5.6 (s, 2-H), 2.3 (s, 6-CH₃); **3c** (55%), m.p. 215°, δ 7.0–8.0 (m, ArH), 5.5 (s, 2-H), 2.3 (s, 6-CH₃); **3d** (55%), m.p. 160°, δ 7.1–8.3 (m, ArH), 5.6 (s, 2-H), 2.3 (s, 6-CH₃); **3e** (53%), m.p. 190°, δ 6.8–8.0 (m, ArH), 5.5 (s, 2-H), 2.3 (s, 6-CH₃), 4.0 (s, OCH₃).

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